

Epidemiology of Bone Hydatidosis in Eastern Libya from 1995 to 2013

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Abstract : Bone hydatidosis is an infection in worldwide distribution. Although there is no evidence in literature on Bone Hydatid disease in Libya, we tried to present the first epidemiological study of this disease in Eastern Libya through retrospective study from 1995 to 2013. Our data were collected from 3 hospitals in Eastern Libya particularly the sheep-raising areas with total number of musculoskeletal infection cases of two thousand one hundred ninety-four (2,194). There were five (5) five cases of bone infection, four (4) of it have been diagnosed after more than three (3) months. Our study is comparable to other international study but this type of bone infection need further studies for effective control strategies for all dogs to avoid serious complications that might happened from the delay in diagnosing this type of disease.

Keywords : bone infection, hydatidosis, Eastern Libya, sheep-raising areas

Conference Title : ICOSBCA 2014 : International Conference on Orthopaedic Surgery, Biomechanics and Clinical Applications

Conference Location : Bangkok, Thailand

Conference Dates : December 24-25, 2014